

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE USE OF TABLES AS A UNIVERSAL TOOL FOR CONSOLIDATING PUNCTUATION RULES IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE CLASS IN UPPER SECONDARY SCHOOL

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Abstract

The article examines the potential of using tables as a means of summarising linguistic knowledge among upper secondary school students in order to develop a holistic and systematic understanding of the Russian language. The author emphasises that tables can be employed in both traditional and innovative ways in Russian language teaching and demonstrates how they may be used to make the consolidation of linguistic knowledge more interactive and engaging for learners at the upper secondary level. The study concludes that working with tables represents a universal technique for knowledge systematisation and, in the era of educational digitalisation, is becoming increasingly relevant as a means of enhancing students' cognitive development.

Keywords: teaching Russian in upper secondary school; consolidation of linguistic knowledge; developing a systematic understanding of the Russian language; tables as a tool for knowledge consolidation; traditional and innovative approaches to using tables in Russian language class.

The systematic approach to teaching Russian at school involves the sequential study of all language levels (phonetics and graphics, vocabulary, morphemics, word formation, morphology, spelling, punctuation, syntax, and stylistics), which are closely interconnected. Pupils gradually develop this systematic understanding of the language by the time they reach the upper years, having studied each level in turn throughout the core Russian language course from Years 5 to 9. In Years 10–11, the primary educational objective shifts towards consolidating previously acquired knowledge in order to develop a holistic understanding of language as a system and as one of the fundamental values of the contemporary world. The extent to which students have developed generalised linguistic knowledge and the corresponding skills and competencies is assessed through the Unified State Examination (USE).

The issue of knowledge consolidation in Russian language teaching remains highly relevant, as it is closely associated with pupils' acquisition of linguistic knowledge, the ways in which contemporary learners perceive and process information [4], and the development of their cognitive abilities. Methods of consolidation as an essential final stage in mastering linguistic knowledge are discussed extensively in leading textbooks on Russian language teaching methodology by A. V. Tekuchev [10], M. T. Baranov [7], and in the handbook edited by R. B. Sabatkov [11], among others. Approaches to the consolidation of linguistic information in Russian language lessons have also been explored by numerous scholars in the field, including O. Y. Dubova [3], N. V. Medvedeva and L. S. Fominykh [6], I. A. Sotova [8], N. V. Sulnichenko [9], E. V. Khomenko [12], and others. This study adopts the definition of consolidation proposed by M. R. Lvov in his *Methodological Dictionary*, where it is described as “a

teaching technique based on the cognitive operation of generalisation and enabling learners to understand structural relationships within a language” [5, p. 139].

Contemporary Russian language teaching methodology offers a wide range of approaches to knowledge consolidation, which may broadly be classified as either traditional or innovative. Traditional approaches include the use of clusters, algorithms, diagrams, tables, and reference guides, whereas innovative approaches encompass virtual excursions, the creation of educational videos on Russian language topics, linguistic games, and mind maps. The emergence of innovative consolidation techniques has largely been driven by advances in digital technologies and the broader processes of globalisation.

The present article examines how tables can be employed as a universal tool for knowledge consolidation and how work with tables can be made more dynamic and interactive, thereby increasing pupils' engagement in the learning process.

In Russian language teaching methodology, a table is commonly defined as “a type of visual teaching aid [...] used both for the introduction of new material and for its consolidation; it serves as an orienting framework for learners' actions” [1, p. 336].

When consolidating knowledge of punctuation rules governing complex sentences, tables may be employed as a traditional teaching tool in the following ways:

- 1) Studying a completed table provided in a textbook or a Unified State Examination (USE) preparation guide, or a table prepared by the teacher on the basis of such materials. This approach is particularly effective at the beginning of the consolidation process, when students' prior knowledge is being activated;

An example is presented below [2, p. 94]:

Table 1

Punctuation in Asyndetic Complex Sentences (i.e. complex sentences where clauses are not linked by conjunctions) in Russian

Use a comma	Use a semicolon	Use a colon	Use a dash
Between clauses that are closely related in meaning and describe a sequence of actions, events, or facts.	To emphasise the semantic independence of individual clauses.	When the second clause explains, clarifies, specifies, or gives the reason for what is stated in the first clause.	When the second clause presents an unexpected result, consequence, contrast, or sudden change of events.
	If the clauses, which are not closely related in meaning, consist of semantically connected simple sentences linked by commas, or if they are sufficiently extended and contain numerous homogeneous elements or parenthetical constructions.	With explanatory intonation, when the second clause explains, supplements, or clarifies the content of the first clause.	If the second clause summarises the content of the first clause, expresses a consequence, or contains a sharp contrast.
		With anticipatory intonation, if the second clause is preceded by an implied meaning equivalent to the verbs <i>see</i> , <i>hear</i> , <i>believe</i> , etc.	If the content of the second clause is conditioned by that of the first clause.
		If the second clause takes the form of a direct question.	When there is an evaluative comparison between the individual clauses.

2) Identifying the rule or condition that accounts for the use of a particular punctuation mark in an example of a complex sentence. This activity is most appropriate at the initial stage of applying theoretical knowledge in practice, when learners still benefit from articulating the rules governing punctuation between clauses in a clear and systematic manner;

3) Creating or copying a table into a notebook under the teacher's guidance. This can be carried out after students have become familiar with a completed table and serves to record theoretical rules in one's own notebook.

An alternative approach to consolidating knowledge of punctuation in complex sentences through the use of tables, one that may better reflect the expectations and learning preferences of contemporary students, is based on interactive engagement. Such an approach involves both direct teacher-student interaction in the form of collaborative dialogue and the integration of digital technologies into the learning process. Within this framework, work with tables may be organised in a variety of ways.

1) Adding students' own examples to a table on the basis of a pre-selected text (text extract) from Russian classical literature. This activity is particularly suitable at the final stage of activating and reviewing theoretical knowledge;

2) Constructing a table collaboratively on the board using printed fragments containing punctuation rules and corresponding examples. In this case, the table is assembled as a kind of puzzle or construction

task. This interactive alternative to traditional note-taking may also be used during the activation of prior knowledge;

3) Adding exceptions to a table during classroom discussion. This approach may be implemented while practising punctuation rules. For example, students may encounter a compound sentence in which a comma is not required between clauses because they share a common secondary sentence element, such as an adverbial modifier of time or place. Recording such exceptions within the table helps learners refine and extend their understanding of the rule;

4) Creating a table within a digital presentation with the use of animation and audio support in collaboration with the teacher during classroom dialogue. This method is particularly effective during the review stage. The completed table can then be used throughout the consolidation lesson, as the slides remain visible while students work on practical tasks (similar approach to using tables as a means of knowledge consolidation is described by O. Y. Dubova) [3];

5) Transforming a table into an algorithm in order to promote a deeper understanding of the underlying theory. This interactive approach, discussed by I. A. Sotova [8] and V. N. Sulnichenko [9], makes it possible to assess the extent to which students understand both the classification principles underlying the table and the theoretical material as a whole. Such a creative task is most appropriately carried out at the final stage of a consolidation lesson. As a result, students studying the topic "Punctuation in Complex Sentences" are provided with two complementary ways of organising theoretical knowledge and may subsequently choose

whichever format they find most useful when preparing for the USE.

The versatility of tables as a means of consolidating linguistic knowledge lies in their ability to help pupils identify the key conceptual categories that underpin the application of punctuation rules, as reflected in the structure of rows and columns. Tables also provide a clear visual representation of the similarities and differences between punctuation rules governing complex sentences, draw attention to particularly challenging cases and exceptions, and facilitate a more systematic understanding of punctuation as a whole. In addition, their use may contribute to improved language accuracy by reducing the number of errors made in situations that are traditionally regarded as difficult.

From a methodological perspective, it would be inappropriate to regard tables exclusively as either a traditional or an innovative teaching tool. As the approaches discussed above demonstrate, the educational value of tables lies precisely in the variety of ways in which they can be integrated into the learning process. Depending on the instructional design, the same tool may fulfil different pedagogical functions and be perceived by learners in different ways.

It can therefore be concluded that work with tables may serve both as a traditional and as an innovative means of consolidating linguistic knowledge in Russian language education. Although the use of tables has long been established as a conventional teaching practice, it continues to encourage active engagement with and synthesis of linguistic information. At the same time, within the contemporary educational environment, this approach can acquire an innovative dimension through the incorporation of interactive methods. Such methods include not only direct interaction between a teacher and pupils, but also collaborative learning among pupils and the use of information and communication technologies, including computers, projectors, audio equipment, and other digital resources. The methodological need to rethink and adapt approaches to working with tables in the consolidation of linguistic knowledge at the upper secondary level is largely associated with the rapid development of digital technologies and the increasing influence of digital learning environments on educational practice. Under these conditions, the table remains a highly effective and adaptable pedagogical tool, capable of supporting both knowledge consolidation and students' cognitive development.

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